

DIPLOMATIC ETUQUETTE AS AN IMPORTANT TOOL OF DIPLOMATIC RELATIONS

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Annotation. This article reflects on the rules of diplomatic etiquette as well as the guidelines for compliance, the main place in the field of diplomacy as an example of different countries.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada diplomatik etiket qoidalari hamda ularga rioya qilish borasida ko’rsatmalar, diplomatiya sohasida asosiy o’rinni egallashi turli davlatlar misoli bo’yicha mulohaza yuritilgan.

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Diplomatic etiquette is the rules of good conduct that apply during the dialogues of diplomats and other officials at diplomatic events with each other. Diplomatic etiquette relies on general etiquette rules in the process of formation, while diplomatic norms and rules are reflected in business etiquette practice and general etiquette rules. Violations of these rules cannot be allowed, the impossibility of ordinary formality in relations is equated with disrespect in diplomatic etiquette and is able to create international and interethnic conflicts.

Particular attention is paid to compliance with the rules of etiquette by diplomats, since violation or non-fulfillment of these rules can undermine the prestige of its official representatives of the country, as a result, lead to a violation of relations between countries. Diplomatic etiquette is diverse. It covers meetings, mutual salute exchange, farewell addresses, reception ceremonies, visitation, conversation and negotiation etiquette, and diplomatic ceremonies. Diplomacy is the art of making mutual agreements, agreements and conventions. These results are achieved at the successful end of the meetings.

Diplomatic meetings are characterized by their own established regulation, etiquette, and often their own protocol. The main reason for this is that the participants in diplomatic meetings adhere regardless of the subordination rules and professional restrictions that form the basis of such a delicate activity as diplomacy. Meetings begin with a mutual exchange of greetings. The types of greetings will be different. A person who is on a long trip in foreign countries compares the National traditions and laws of this country with the customs of his country.

When a reception ceremony is being organized in honor of a person or in cases where it is offered to a guest, it is necessary to know which religion the guest adheres

to. According to Islamic rules, alcohol consumption is strictly prohibited. According to the rules of the Hindu religion, the dishes should be of a vegetarian type and not prepared from beef.

Diplomatic salute exchange rules are practically no different from the general salute exchange rules. First, the name of the person to be introduced is pronounced middle name, and then the name of the person to whom it is introduced is middle name. A younger person is introduced to an older person, a male to a female person, a lower person in terms of position is introduced to a higher person in terms of position.

The person being introduced bows with his head slightly bent if there is a man, while the woman is content with his head slightly bent. If a woman intends to get to know someone who is interested in her, she may ask about introducing someone who is familiar to both of them. Someone who is familiar with the two helps to have a conversation based on their circle of interest. Since bowing the head while sitting is almost uncomfortable, a man should stand up when he is dating.

A woman, on the contrary, should not stand her ground. An exception is when a woman older than her age is introduced to a woman, or when she wants to express her special opinion about the person being introduced. In these cases, he can stand up and reach for a greeting. In cases where a man is introduced to a man, a woman hands a greeting if she finds it appropriate for her, otherwise she is content with a slightly bowed greeting on her head. In the rest of the cases, the older person reaches for the first hand to say hello.

The person entering the room greets those who first gather. The first person to leave is surprised by the crowd. When introducing a person to others, it is necessary not only to limit yourself to saying the sheriff of his full name, but also to briefly talk about the qualities inherent in this person, the ground is also laid for the continuation of the conversation, and the exchange of ideas of new acquaintances becomes a little easier.

If at a diplomatic reception it is necessary to introduce two people whose age and position are equal, it is necessary to first introduce someone who is closer or who is relatively familiar. If one of the introductions is a celebrity, one can be limited to introducing the other to her. During practical or protocol meetings (dating or admiration meetings), a conversation is conducted.

The conversation is not subject to regulation due to many situations. But it is a pity that both visitors to the meeting and their recipients take note of some of the rules that apply to them. The visit of the eunuch, veneration or protocol is not long, that is, it is necessary that it does not exceed 20, at most 30 minutes. Diplomatic ceremonial (ceremonial ceremonies) are considered ceremonial, with diverse,

complex, subtleties. The development of the requirements of diplomatic protocol embodies the rules of Customs, statehood and universally adopted behavior.

The habit of organizing receptions came to us from the past, was considered a sign of pacifism, good. Hospitality, to this day, has been an indicator of the honor of the state and the fullness of the people. The reluctance of the traditional dishes of the guest at official reception ceremonies indicates a special respect for the guest State.

Currently, in international practice, there are several types of formal receptions that are required to be performed for all participants and are specific to their label. During diplomatic receptions, a conversation is conducted, negotiations, dating and other activities are carried out that are not clearly defined.

Participants are limited to each other's interaction, meeting character, age, telling each other their full names, or just saying their last names.

The character of a diplomatic meeting or Diplomatic Reception determines the norm and form of interaction, the level of greeting.

One meeting is entirely informal, another – semi – formal, and the third-held in a manner predetermined by the protocol. The label is clear and does not look for the same recommendations.

According to the diplomatic label, the main condition for treatment is related to the type of admission.

The main condition for behavior is associated with the reception ceremony according to diplomatic etiquette.

Reception ceremonies are aimed at establishing and developing relations between representatives of the diplomatic corps and with foreign representatives of the official government. Reception ceremonies are held to celebrate an event, such as a visit to the country by the head of state or government, or on the occasion of the holiday and anniversary dates, in honor of signing any document, as a sign of respect for celebrities.

"Diplomatic protocol" -the Basic Rules of relations in interstate cooperation, including respect for sovereignty, equality, freedom, territorial stability, non-interference in each other's internal affairs, would not have been able to implement a full-fledged agreement without observing the requirements. To fulfill such requirements, in addition to experience in this regard, a certain guideline is also necessary.

Such a program is called a diplomat (negotiation) statement. This statement is a set of rules that cover both processed, years of editing and experience of interoperability, from the emergence of the state to the present period, and modern requirements.

The "diplomatic dictionary" is able to give a more accurate understanding of the diplomat's statement: a diplomatic statement is a set of the rule of a universally

accepted tradition and customs, which must be carried out in international relations by officials, representatives, governments. The essence of the negotiation statement is that in their relationship the agreements of the states are transmitted within the framework of moral culture, that is, to conduct the agreements of the states in a beautiful way – without leaving moral standards. In fact, the minutes were used to properly shape the documents, to archive them. As the periods grew, this type of statement, which he used to negotiate, was formed in a wide range of content and also began to be used as a etiquette of celebration and negotiation.

By the present time, the minutes of negotiations have become different in nature, influenced by scientific and technical progress, mainly by modern requirements, with political and legal changes. But these changes are not any statewide principles, which have an unjustified nature, but rather an experimental basis, which are universally accepted rules on a global scale.

Officially, however, the negotiation protocol was approved by the Congress of Vienna in 1814. The negotiation statement embodied etiquette and solemnity in itself. The main part of the negotiation statement, the negotiation etiquette, is the beautiful behavior and behavior of the representatives of the state, manifested in their relationship.

The rules of the negotiation label covered everything from the external dress of the negotiator representative to the etiquette of gesture, behavior. Treatment in the negotiation label is characterized in different manifestations of the negotiation – according to writing, meeting, reception and visit. A Zero Statesman is obliged to adequately respond to any types of negotiations from a representative of another state, to consider them. The very act of not responding to a letter or proposal is considered extremely indecent. Sincerity and immediacy are of great importance in this.

Each country has its own label principles and they are an integral part of an international label.

France. While France is considered the label's homeland, it does not receive as much attention as in other countries. For several centuries, France has maintained the view that “the manner in which a Frenchman behaves is a label”. French is a language of world and diplomacy. In this regard, the French believe that nothing has changed.

UK. The main qualities of the English include self-control, the ability not to convey what he wants to say to the interlocutor to the end, the ability to keep his problems inside, insufficient openness, appreciation of property, independence.

Conclusion. The rules of the negotiation label covered everything from the external dress of the negotiator representative to the etiquette of gesture, behavior. Treatment in the negotiation label is characterized in different manifestations of the

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